

Marketing 4.0: A Perfect Blend of Style and Substance

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ABSTRACT

Marketing 4.0 is a new approach where the customers have an offline interaction with the companies. Digital technology has changed the lives of most modern businesses and humans alike. With the advent of technologies like IoT, mobile internet, cloud tech, etc. Marketing has moved from the conformist product-centric approaches to the human-centric era where humans via the 24*7 mobile internets are constantly in touch even offline with the brands they support. The new mantra of –"Marketing 4.0 blending style and substance" has exemplified the new role of consumers, who want to be a part of the marketing experience and be associated with the brands they promote. The companies also support the consumers' needs by customizing services and prices. This review acknowledges that digital innovation has made its impact on large corporate firms and SMEs alike, but the downside is implementing the rubrics of Marketing 4.0 especially issues such as cost of implementation; general reluctance towards digital marketing transformation; poor infrastructure in developing countries, etc. Therefore marketing strategy must involve consumers, company employees, and shareholders as stakeholders in this whole process.

Keywords: Marketing 4.0; Digital Marketing

INTRODUCTION

Kotler et al (2010) have coined this mantra of –"Marketing 4.0-when Online meets offline, style meets substance, and Machine –to – Machine meets Human –to- Human".

Lately, Covid-19 infection and the prevailing digital boom has unsettled key industries like music, retail, movies, and even brick and mortar retail stores and malls resulting in job losses. People are closeted at home and are spending more time on the mobile internet which has affected relationships as their attention is constantly diverted towards their mobiles increasing their anxiety levels and decreased empathy echelons. But this has benefited the digital economy which is a new trend fuelled by advanced telecommunication (mobile phones, faster internet, and faster transportation), which is the major driver for the retail economy (Dunn, 2015).

Furthermore, digital technology has changed the lives of most modern businesses and humans alike. With the advent of technologies like IoT, mobile internet, cloud tech, etc. Marketing has moved from the conformist product-centric approaches to the human-centric era where humans via the 24*7 mobile internets are constantly in touch even offline with the brands they support (Kotler et al .,2017).

Traditionally marketing by most companies had a vertical approach dominated by the company where they used to target and segment the customers according to their brand. A brand is explained as a company's service or merchandise with a distinct logo or image or tagline which generates a certain value over years; in short, the consumers' experience of the products that the company delivers(Kotler et al .,2017).

But due to digital marketing consumers have now got an upper hand as they effectually participate in the community of consumers and demand transparency where the company brand promises are in question and do not take anything lightly. The companies on the other hand have also started catering to different consumer's price-wise and efficient methods of home delivery of products. The consumers are as involved as the company, especially in the promotion and sale of the brands via consumer rating experiences (Kotler et al .,2017).

Marketing 4.0 is a new approach where the customers have an offline interaction with the companies. Customers seek features of flexibility, authenticity, and adaptability in the brands of their choice and this need is fulfilled by artificial intelligence which has enhanced the whole marketing efficiency at the same time leveraging the consumer's commitment towards the whole process (Kotler et al .,2017). Thus this review is going to delve into the concept of Marketing 4.0 and its implications.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing concepts over the decades

In 1971, the definition of Marketing, coined by Denner (Balaure, V., 2002) dealt with the demand and the means to satisfy the demands of the consumer and this has evolved to marketing strategy should be specifically designed to identify and satisfy consumer demands profitably (Chartered Institute of Marketing, 2015). Marketing has evolved into a more managerial and social approach to try and create value for customers by taking the support of IT technologies like Machine learning and Artificial intelligence to increase yield.

The Internet has opened up a global market to the consumers and even small companies can compete with the large corporations to gain the attention of the consumers. These competitions have made them think out of the box and are forced to create niche marketing to cater to the needs of the customers (Kotler et al., 2017).

Marketing 4.0 and the Customer experience

The marketing managers have to consider consumers as being the focal point of the marketing strategy 4.0 and treat them as co-creators of the whole marketing experience as they expect more interaction in the form of dialogue and cooperation by the company (Tarabasz, 2013). As almost sixty-five percent of the internet marketers are 35 years and younger, and economically better placed, perceive e-media as an invaluable tool for their shopping needs. Being media savvy the buyers demand more product information, transparencies, personalization of the products to their needs- has put a strain on the market reality. The companies on the other hand generally view social media as one of the channels for marketing and still believe in the old principle that people buy for rational reasons and have downplayed the role of social media as a marketing tool. (Tarabasz, 2013)

Small and medium enterprises (SME) and their 4.0 experience

Świeczak (2017) has elaborated on the idea of how SME and the new millennia's are handling the marketing 4.0 experience. Digital innovations (read- social, mobile, analytics, and cloud) are forcing even the SME to reinvent them to a certain level of digital maturity to stay relevant according to the new generation of shoppers.

The results of this study showed that seventy-two percent of millennia have used the internet for information and 69.8% for entertainment. 90.89% use Facebook every day and more than half of the users do pay attention to the marketing actions of various enterprises. 46.2% show intention to buy due to the advertisements and 24% end up buying the service or product.

This study was done on SME's with less than 250 employees and Facebook was used 20.5% and LinkedIn 12.4% for marketing purposes by the managers. The SMEs in their defense- 58.5 % are trying to implement the Marketing 4.0 strategy but only 9.8% are concentrating on the marketing technologies. This can be attributed to the fact that 40% wants cutbacks on the unit cost of the product as they depend mostly on internal resources; they have issues on the financial stability of the company after implementing changes; corporate security issues, and a general reluctance towards digital marketing transformation.

Marketing 4.0 and the Russian transport experience

In Russia, only 69.9% of members of the transport industry communicated with partners using internet tools. This reservation can be attributed to the cost associated with the implementation of advanced digital technology in this industry (Heddebaut, 2017).

Marketing 4.0 Country-wide variation

In the Czech Republic (ČSÚ, 2016), twenty percent have innovated marketing methods where three-fourths concentrate on new media techniques, followed by packaging, and very little attention is paid to the valuation of the product and services. In Denmark, 76% is focused on market innovation methods but only 13% implement these innovations, and that too for online more than offline marketing (Junge et al, 2016). So the point we are trying to make is does market innovation help? (Aksoy & Cengiz, 2016) or is it better to focus on the consumer profile (Anna & Fang, 2016) due to their heterogeneous needs and awareness?

Marketing 4.0 and Developing Countries

In developing countries like Botswana, the cultured customers and their demands are difficult to meet because of the cost involved with implementing new technology in the retail sector due to unskilled labor, inflation, economic environment, poor infrastructure, high rental charges, competition with foreign companies, lack of product differentiation as most people sold the same products, intense price competition, etc. (Phambuka-Nsimbi et al., 2015)

Summary

In summary...

- The informed consumer of today wants the best of products and services available to them even at their doorstep, and the freedom to purchase offline or online anywhere and anytime.
- They demand authenticity, agility, and responsiveness from the market.
- They want to be valued as advocates and promoters of the brands they like by being active on social media and forming fan clubs of the brands.
- A marketing strategy cannot be made in isolation by a selected few; it has to involve consumers, company employees, shareholders as stakeholders in this whole process.

CONCLUSION

"Consumer is king" -this phrase has been known to every marketing rule in the book, but the new mantra of – "Marketing 4.0 blending style and substance" has exemplified the new role of consumers, who want to be a part of the marketing experience and be associated with the brands they promote. The companies also support the consumers' needs by customizing services and prices. This review provides a compendium on the matters that surround Marketing 4.0. and acknowledges that digital innovation has made its impact on large corporate firms and SMEs alike, but the downside is implementing the rubrics of Marketing 4.0 especially issues such as cost of implementation; general reluctance towards digital marketing transformation; poor infrastructure in developing countries, etc. Therefore marketing strategy must involve consumers, company employees, and shareholders as stakeholders in this whole process.

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